

MESOPHASE PITCH-BASED CARBON FIBER
FOR CARBON-CARBON APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Low modulus mesophase pitch-based carbon fiber (MPBCF) is more suitable for carbon-carbon (C/C) composite mainly for two reasons, lower cost and easy handling in weaving and forming.

"DIALEAD K321", low modulus MPBCF can be easily converted into ultra high modulus and high thermal conductivity carbon fiber after heat treatment without tension.

This paper describes the development of crystallographic, physical and mechanical properties of "DIALEAD K321" after heat treatment in comparison with other pitch-based or PAN-based carbon fibers. Unique behavior of "DIALEAD K321" after heat treatment is discussed. Excellent performance of C/C composites made of "DIALEAD K321" is also described.

KEYWORDS: Carbon fiber; Fiber structure; Thermal conductivity;
C/C composites

1. INTRODUCTION

At present, there are three types of commercial carbon fibers: Pitch-based type, polyacrylonitrile-based type and rayon-based type. The Amoco's petroleum pitch-based carbon fibers pioneered the market of pitch-based carbon fibers. On the other hand, the Mitsubishi Kasei Corporation (MKC) has started its commercial production of coal tar pitch-based carbon fibers "DIALEAD" in 1987. Since then, "DIALEAD" has been used in many kinds of applications like carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) for golf shaft, carbon fiber reinforced cement for building, C/C composites for brake, because it has good processability and good mechanical and physical properties. The properties of C/C composite mainly depend on those of the base carbon fiber. For C/C composite, the important properties of carbon fiber are primary processability and its characteristics like higher strength, higher modulus, higher thermal conductivity, higher carbon content, purity and so on. "DIALEAD K321" is produced from the similar precursor for ultra high modulus fiber. Therefore, "DIALEAD K321" can be easily converted into ultra high modulus and high strength carbon fiber by heat treatment process, also shows good processability during C/C composite manufacturing. C/C composite with higher thermal conductivity can be obtained by heat treatment in woven fabric and uni-directional substrate made of "DIALEAD K321". Uni-directional C/C composite, "MFC-1" has the higher thermal conductivity as well as less impurities, therefore it is suitable for plasma-facing materials for nuclear fusion reactor. C/C brakes made of "DIALEAD K321" has better abrasion resistance and oxidation resistance.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Specimens

The three kinds of low modulus carbon fiber used in this study are coal tar pitch-based carbon fiber "DIALEAD K321" (DIALEAD fiber), petroleum pitch-based carbon fiber (PETROLEUM PITCH fiber), and polyacrylonitrile-based carbon fiber (PAN fiber).

2.2 Heat treatment

Carbon fiber properties vary with heat treatment process in manufacturing C/C composite. So, we measured crystallographic, physical and mechanical properties in the three kinds of carbon fiber after heat treatment.

The heating rate was 250°C per hour from room temperature to 1000°C and 50°C per hour from 1000°C to various temperatures.

After one hour holding at each maximum temperature, the cooling rate was 300°C per hour.

Specimens were set in the graphite box without tension.

2.3 Fiber properties

Tensile properties of carbon fibers were measured by Japanese Industrial Standard (JIS R 7601 6.6.1).

Thermal conductivity of carbon fibers was measured as CFRP by the laser flash method at room temperature.

2.4 Fiber structure observation

Longitudinal cross sections along the carbon fiber axis were observed by transmission electron microscopy. Crystallite sizes of carbon fibers were measured by X-ray diffraction technique.

2.5 Oxidation resistance

The oxidation resistance of carbon fibers was measured by thermogravimetric (TGA) analysis method. Sample weight was ca. 10mg. Heating rate was 10°C per minute in air atmosphere. Carbon content was measured by CHN analyzer, impurities were measured by atomic emission spectroscopy and atomic absorption spectrometry.

2.6 C/C composite properties

We made C/C brake discs made of the three kinds of carbon fiber by the same process described in MKC's patent (Ref.1).

Wearness and coefficient of friction were measured by disc-disc friction test apparatus. Test conditions are as follows:

Surface Pressure = 1Pa

Circumferential Velocity = 8m/sec

Wear loss (abrasion) was measured thickness of disc after friction test. Coefficient of friction was calculated from the torque.

We made uni-directional C/C composite, "MFC-1" of DIALEAD fiber by heat treatment at high temperature. Thermal conductivities of "MFC-1" were measured by the laser flash method. Flexural properties were measured by the three-point flexural method.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fiber properties after heat treatment

The tensile strength of DIALEAD fiber increased almost linearly with heat treatment temperature. That of PETROLEUM PITCH fiber increased slightly. That of PAN fiber didn't changed (Figure-1).

The tensile modulus of DIALEAD fiber steady raised with heat treatment temperature. That of PETROLEUM PITCH fiber raised slightly. That of PAN fiber raised slightly (Figure-2). In the production of DIALEAD fibers, the good orientation of liquid crystal is given to the fibers by spinning process so that mechanical properties after heat treatment can increase without tension. Higher tensile strength and modulus of PETROLEUM PITCH fiber and PAN fiber might achieve with tension under heat treatment.

Figure-1 Tensile Strength after Heat Treatment

Figure-2 Tensile Modulus after Heat Treatment

3.2 Fiber structures after heat treatment

Transmission electron micrographs of longitudinal cross section along the carbon fiber axis are shown in Figure-3. In these pictures, DIALEAD fiber has better prefered orientation of aromatic layers parallel to fiber axis. On the contrary, PAN fiber has poor orientation of aromatic layers in the random direction. The results of X-ray crystalline analyses in Figure-4 clearly demonstrate the difference of crystallite size among three fibers after heat treatment. Crystallite size L_c increases with an increase in heat treatment temperature. DIALEAD fiber has the largest crystallite size among three fibers after heat treatment. Those behaviors depend on the difference of precursor's molecular structure.

Figure-3 Transmission Electron Microscopy of Carbon fiber after heat treatment at 3000°C

Figure-4 Crystallite size L_c after Heat Treatment

3.3 Thermal conductivity after heat treatment

Thermal conductivity increases with an increase in heat treatment temperature. DIALEAD fiber has the highest thermal conductivity among three fibers after heat treatment (Figure-5). Those behaviors are similar to those of crystallite size. The relation between thermal conductivity and crystallite size L_c is shown in Figure-6. All fibers have the same relationship. Thermal conductivity increases in proportion to phonon mean free path that is determined by concentration of the defects. The defects which scatter phonon are on the decrease, when crystal has grown up.

Figure-5 Thermal Conductivity after Heat Treatment

Figure-6 The Relation between Thermal Conductivity and Crystallite size L_c

3.4 Oxidation resistance

TGA weight loss curves of three carbon fibers are shown in Figure-7. The weight loss of DIALEAD fiber shows less amount than the other fibers. The fibers with high carbon content and low metal content possess the highest resistance to oxidation (Ref.2). The results of element analysis of three carbon fibers are shown in Table-1. DIALEAD fiber had high carbon content and less impurities.

Figure-7 Oxidation Resistance of Various Carbon Fibers

Table-1 Carbon Fiber Element Assay

	DIALEAD	PETROLEUM PITCH	PAN
CARBON %	>99	>99	>93
Si ppm	10	3	>100
Al ppm	10	10	100
Fe ppm	1	3	10
Na ppm	nd	3	10
K ppm	nd	3	10
800°C-15min Ash %	<0.1	<0.1	0.1

3.5 C/C Composite's Properties

The results of C/C composite brake disc-disc friction test are shown in Figure-8. C/C brake disc made of DIALEAD fiber shows not only less weariness, but also higher coefficient of friction.

It turned out that the wear loss of C/C brake disc made of low crystalline carbon fibers increase enormously. Low crystalline carbon fibers might make thick layer of friction. The wear loss of C/C brake disc made of PAN fiber was about five times as that of DIALEAD fiber. The Coefficient of friction is affected by the surface temperature of the disc. Higher thermal conductivity and higher thermal capacity of DIALEAD fiber might bring higher coefficient of friction to C/C brake disc.

The most severe conditions of brake disc are given in Formula One races (F1). F1 car brake requires the stability of friction at high temperature. Therefore the C/C brake made of carbon fibers with high thermal conductivity is the most suitable brake for F1 car. C/C brake disc and pad made of DIALEAD fiber for F1 car are shown in Figure-9.

Figure-8 Friction Properties of Disc-Disc Friction Test

Figure-9 C/C Brake Disc and Pad for F1 Car made by MKC

The properties of "MFC-1" made of DIALEAD fiber are shown in Table-2. "MFC-1" has the higher thermal conductivity as well as less impurities. Therefore "MFC-1" is suitable for plasma-facing materials for nuclear fusion reactor. It is currently used some experimental reactor like JT-60(Japan) and JET(EC). "MFC-1" is also one of the most favorite candidates for the first wall or the divertor material of ITER.

Table-2 Properties of "MFC-1"

Properties	Direction	
	fiber angle 0°	fiber angle 90°
Thermal Conductivity(W/m K)	550	40
Flexual Modulus(GPa)	100	1
Flexual Strength(MPa)	490	5
Bulk Density(g/cm)	1.96	
Ash Content(ppm)	< 20	

4. CONCLUSIONS

The properties of carbon-carbon composite depend on those of the base carbon fiber.

"DIALEAD K321" is the most suitable fiber for carbon-carbon applications.

Reasons

- 1) After heat treatment without tension "DIALEAD K321" achieves the higher strength(4000MPa), higher modulus(800GPa) and higher thermal conductivity(500W/m K).
- 2) "DIALEAD K321" has the higher carbon content.(99%)
- 3) "DIALEAD K321" is free of impurities.
(Ash content is less than 0.1%)

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